

Another perspective on the relations of personality to suicides, suicide attempts, and suicide ideations

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The relative frequency of suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts differs widely. This has prompted researchers to assume that both common and divergent factors such as personality might influence the occurrence of these four types of suicidal phenomena. The present geographical psychology study examined the relationship between personality and these suicidal events using the 50 American states as analytical units. Based on 2008-2009 data, relations of rates of suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts to the Big Five personality variables and six sociodemographic variables (i.e., socioeconomic status, White population percent, urban population percent, unemployment rate, religiosity, and depression) were determined using sequential multiple regression. Separate analyses were conducted for five population categories: total, male, female, younger, and older. In each equation, the six sociodemographic variables are entered first as a block. The Big Five entered second stepwise. The results showed a high degree of consistency across the five population categories. For example, *lower* neuroticism and lower agreeableness were associated with higher suicide rates in all five, but neither neuroticism nor agreeableness was related to suicide attempts, plans, or thoughts in any of the five. The magnitude of the suicide rate variance accounted for by neuroticism and agreeableness far exceeded the variance accounted for by the block of six socioeconomic variables, even though the personality variables had the disadvantage of entering the equation after the six socioeconomic controls. It is cautiously speculated that these state-level relations are grounded in corresponding relations at the individual level of analysis. As well, it is suggested that clinicians may miss the mark somewhat if they are not particularly vigilant for suicide risk signs in clients from states with characteristically lower resident neuroticism or lower agreeableness, in those who are less neurotic or more disagreeable, or in those who do not outwardly display evidence of attempted suicide or suicidal ideation.

Keywords: neuroticism; personality; suicide; suicide attempts; suicide ideations

There are large differences in the frequencies of suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicidal thoughts in the US. For example, in 2018, there were 48,244 suicides, but approximately 1,300,000 adults attempted suicide, 2,800,000 made suicide plans, and 9,800,000 had serious suicidal thoughts. As well, of the 1,300,000 who attempted suicide, it is estimated that 300,000 attempted suicide without developing any previous suicide plan (National Institute of Mental Health, 2019). Therefore, it is not surprising that researchers have assumed that there might be divergent *and* common factors underlying these four categories of suicidal phenomena (e.g., Branley-Bell et al., 2019; Conner et al., 2007; Marie et al., 2020).

One such line of enquiry has centred on the role of the Big Five personality dimensions (e.g., Costa & McCrae, 1995; Goldberg, 1990; John & Srivastava, 1999) in relation to suicide, suicide attempts, and suicidal thoughts, and plans. The well-established Big Five model comprises five major personality dimensions: openness to experience; conscientiousness; extraversion; agreeableness; and neuroticism. Each continuum consists of several facets. For example, persons higher on openness demonstrate greater diversity tolerance and willingness to experiment; conscientiousness emphasises order and dutifulness; extraversion is gregarious, and excitement is seeking; agreeableness shows greater trust and compliance, and neuroticism is more anxious and vulnerable (Costa & McCrae, 1995).

Neuroticism has been the personality dimension most researched in suicide, with individuals as the units of analysis. For example, despite obvious major obstacles to studying the personality of those who take their own lives (Brezo et al., 2006), researchers usually have found that higher neuroticism is associated with suicides, but there are exceptions. Suicide completers are higher on the neuroticism dimension than comparable controls (e.g., Draper et al., 2014; Duberstein et al., 1994; Tsoh et al., 2005; Useda et al., 2007). Batty et al. (2018) also found that across five large cohort samples containing 464,251 persons observed for an average of 8.1 years, higher neuroticism was associated with a greater number of deaths attributed to suicide. A literature review by Wasserman (2016) concluded that neuroticism was positively related to suicide. However, Tsoh et al. (2005) and Useda et al. (2007) reported that suicide completers are less neurotic than attempters, and Beautrais (2004) found in a sample of suicide attempters followed for five years that neuroticism was unrelated to future suicides.

Studies also tend to support an association between higher neuroticism and suicide attempts in a research area less fraught with procedural difficulties. As noted in the previous paragraph, suicide attempters may be more neurotic than completers (Tsoh et al., 2005; Useda et al., 2007). Beautrais (2004) also found in the sample of suicide attempters who followed for five years that neuroticism was positively related to making further suicide attempts. Su et al. (2018) compared mood disorder patients to community controls and found that higher neuroticism was associated with greater risk for suicide attempts and that this association was elevated among those with suicidal thoughts. In addition, Wasserman's (2016) review also concluded that neuroticism is associated with suicide attempts. However, Rappaport et al. (2017) found in a study of 5,864 Chinese women with major depressive disorder and 5,783 without that neuroticism assessed with the Eysenck measure decreased the chances of a suicide attempt. Somewhat in contrast to research on the relations of neuroticism to suicides and attempted suicides, research rather consistently supports an association between higher neuroticism and aspects of suicidal ideation, which comprises suicide thoughts and plans (e.g., Batterham & Christensen, 2012; Kim & Ahn, 2014; Rappaport et al., 2017; Stefa-Missagli et al., 2019; Su et al., 2018; Wasserman, 2016).

The other Big Five personality factors have received less attention in the realm of suicidal phenomena. Nevertheless, a relatively high number of studies have found that lower extraversion is associated with suicides (e.g., Draper et al., 2014), suicide attempts (e.g., Wiktorsson et al., 2013), and suicide ideations (e.g., Singh & Pathak, 2017). Based on comparatively less research, suicides, suicide attempts, and suicide ideations generally be associated with higher openness (e.g., Bluml et al., 2013; Draper et al., 2014; Rozanov & Mid'ko, 2011), lower conscientiousness (e.g., Cole, Littlefield, Gauthier, & Bragge, 2019; Dutta & Gupta, 2013; Lester, 2001), and lower agreeableness (e.g., Batty et al., 2018; Kerby, 2003; Mousavi et al., 2015). Although support for these relations involving extraversion, openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness is relatively consistent, exceptions also have been reported (e.g., Ayub, 2015; Batty et al., 2018; Bluml et al., 2013; Stankovic et al., 2006; Rozanov & Mid'ko, 2011; Singh & Rani, 2014; Velting, 1999).

Relations between suicide and the Big Five personality dimensions also have been explored within US states rather than individuals as the units of analysis (Lester & Voracek, 2013; McCann, 2010; Voracek, 2009).¹ The

¹Both Voracek (2009) and McCann (2010) asserted that their work was the first to research the relation between state suicide rates and the state-level Big Five personality scores produced by Rentfrow et al. (2008). However, the two articles were conceived and produced on an entirely independent basis. The 'first' claim by McCann (2010) occurred because of a lack of awareness of the publication of the Voracek (2009) article caused by overlapping acceptance, publication, and PsycINFO

main analysis in the Voracek (2009) study used combined suicide rates from 1990 to 1994 as the criterion and included the 50 states and Washington, DC. State gross domestic product (GDP) data from 1999 served as the lone statistical control. Voracek used partial correlation controlling for GDP and the other four Big Five personality variables to determine the link between suicide rates and each Big Five personality dimension. Both partial and Pearson correlation showed that higher suicide rates were associated with *lower* neuroticism. Higher suicide rates showed an association with lower agreeableness using partial correlation, but the relation was not found using Pearson correlation. No other relations between suicide and the Big Five were significant. Voracek (2009) concluded that 'the topic appears worthy of further inquiry' (p. 211).

McCann (2010), also using a geographical psychology approach (Rentfrow, 2010, 2014; Rentfrow et al., 2008; Rentfrow & Jokela, 2016), examined the relation of combined 2004 and 2005 state suicide rates to the Big Five using the 50 states as analytical units. A state composite socioeconomic status (SES) variable based on the years 2000 and 2005, a state White population per cent composite based on 2000 and 2005, a state urban population per cent variable based on 2000, and a state depression rate composite based on 2004 and 2005 served as controls in a sequential multiple regression analytic strategy. Higher suicide rates were associated with *lower* neuroticism and lower agreeableness to a lesser extent in both the Pearson correlation and the multiple regression analysis. Together, state resident neuroticism and agreeableness accounted for a substantial 48% of the variance in 2004 to 2005 state suicide rates.

Lester and Voracek (2013) explored the correlation in the 48 contiguous US states of the state Big Five personality scores (Rentfrow et al., 2008) to suicides in 2008 and to suicide thoughts, suicide plans, and suicide attempts in the 2008–2009 period based on data provided by Crosby et al., (2011). Suicide rates correlated positively with suicide thoughts but did not correlate with suicide plans or attempts. Neuroticism correlated negatively with suicides and suicidal thoughts but did not correlate with suicide plans or attempts. Conscientiousness and suicide plans correlated negatively but this was neither expected nor addressed. Agreeableness was not significantly correlated with any of the four suicide phenomena. Attempted suicide did not correlate with any of the Big Five variables.²

The finding that stands out most in these three studies (i.e., Lester & Voracek, 2013; McCann, 2010; Voracek, 2009) is that higher suicide rates occur in states with *lower* levels of resident neuroticism. There also was a somewhat weaker association between higher suicide rates and lower agreeableness in the Voracek (2009) and McCann (2010) studies. Why should these relations occur? Based on earlier postulations by Useda et al. (2007), who had found in an individual-level study that those who take their own lives were less neurotic than suicide attempters, McCann (2010) speculated that fewer neurotic persons likely have and express less negative emotion and thereby draw relatively less attention to themselves when troubled and considering suicide and that less agreeable persons also are more likely to end their own lives without drawing attention to their plight because of their tendencies to discourage emotional support. Therefore, we should expect suicide-prone persons in less neurotic and less agreeable American states more often to end their own lives without seeking help, and we should expect suicide-prone persons in more neurotic and more agreeable states more often to seek personal or professional assistance and thereby perhaps reduce their chances of suicide.

Formulating expectations for the relations of personality to suicide attempts, plans, and thoughts were more challenging. For example, based on the preponderance of individual-level research evidence that higher neuroticism is associated with suicide attempts (e.g., Su et al., 2018; Useda et al., 2007; Wasserman, 2016) and suicide ideations (e.g., Batterham & Christensen; 2012; Kim & Ahn, 2014; Stefa-Missagli et al., 2019), it was tempting to speculate that similar relations might exist with states as the analytical units. However, individual-level connections were not supported in the state-level research of Lester and Voracek (2013), the only study to examine such relations.

Therefore, even though the exploratory analysis of Lester and Voracek (2013) found no relation between neuroticism and suicide attempts, it seems more likely that higher state resident neuroticism should be associated with higher suicide attempt rates but lower suicide rates. Their Pearson correlation analysis showed no consistent significant correlations between the Big Five personality and the three suicide-related variables.

release dates. The McCann (2010) article was submitted on 26 February 2010, accepted on 30 June 2010, and first published online on 15th November 2010. The Voracek (2009) article was first published on 01 August 2009, but the PsycINFO release date was not until 10 July 2010. McCann was unaware of the Voracek article until a personal communication by Voracek on 09 December 2010, in which he was alerted that the Voracek (2009) article existed.

²Quite surprisingly, Lester and Voracek (2013) did not cite the directly relevant research and speculation of McCann (2010) even though their article was not accepted for publication until 20 March 2013. McCann's e-mail correspondence records show that Voracek had requested and received a copy of the McCann (2010) article on 09 December 2010.

They found no significant correlations between Big Five personality variables and suicide attempts, and only modest significant negative correlations between conscientiousness and suicide plans and between neuroticism and suicide thoughts. Therefore, no expectations were held for personality and the three suicide-related variables in the present state-level research.

The present study

Initiated in the pursuit of greater clarity in this area of inquiry, the present research more comprehensively addressed the relation of state resident Big Five personality to suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts. This study differed in several key respects from the earlier work by Lester and Voracek (2013). For example, the present research used the full complement of 50 states, while Lester and Voracek, without explanation, excluded Alaska and Hawaii even though data were readily available. Also, while Lester and Voracek did not include any covariates in their analysis, the present study included six state demographic controls: SES, White population per cent, urban population per cent, unemployment rate, religiosity, and depression. Finally, while Lester and Voracek used only Pearson correlations, the present study used Pearson correlation and relied strongly on planned sequential multiple regression strategies to further isolate the main relations among the variables. Although theory and past research results suggested, albeit rather equivocally, certain expectations regarding the nature of some of these relations, no firm hypotheses were drawn. Consequently, all the analyses in the present study should be viewed as exploratory.

Another thrust unique to the present research was determining whether relations of the Big Five personality variables to suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts were similar for the whole population, males, females, younger persons, and older persons. For example, some studies with individuals as the analytical units have found that neuroticism is differentially associated with suicide risk, suicide attempts, and suicide ideation according to sex (Bluml et al., 2013, Rozanov & Mid'ko, 2011; Velting, 1999). Others have found that neuroticism is differentially associated with suicides and attempts according to age (Draper et al., 2014; Szucs et al., 2020). Some researchers also report that the prevalence of suicidal ideations is different for males and females (Kim & Burlaka, 2018; Lu et al., 2020) and younger and older persons (Betz et al., 2016; Cukrowicz et al., 2009). The present research examined relations about the general population 18 years of age and over and, for the first time, performed separate analyses for males, females, younger persons aged 18 to 29 years, and older persons aged 30 and above.

Past studies at the individual and/or state level have shown that the six-state demographic controls also may be related to suicides, suicide attempts, suicide thoughts, or suicide plans, as well as one or more of the Big Five personality variables. Suicidal phenomena variables have been found to relate to SES (e.g., McCann, 2010), race (e.g., Woodbury, Manton, & Blazer, 1988), urbanization (e.g., Hedegaard et al., 2018; McCann, 2010), unemployment (e.g., Fountoulakis, 2020; Uysal & Pohlmeier, 2011), religiosity (e.g., Gebauer et al., 2014; Sansone & Wiederman, 2015), and depression (e.g., Klein et al., 2011; McCann, 2010). Therefore, it was reasonable to control for each of these variables at the state level when evaluating the relations of the Big Five personality variables to suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts.

The present research is important from a theoretical and a practical standpoint. There is much room for further contribution focused on untangling the relations of personality factors and other sociodemographic variables to suicides, suicide attempts, and suicidal ideations. Currently, such relations are not well understood in several respects. Such dynamics also may have applied implications. For example, support for the view that state resident differences in personality predict whether state suicide rates or suicide attempt rates are relatively higher or lower would suggest that state suicide reduction programmes perhaps should be tailored somewhat to state resident personality profiles. In addition, healthcare professionals may fall short if they are not cognizant of possible parallel dynamics concerning personality and suicide-related variables at the individual level.

METHODS

Measures

This study is based on 2008 and 2009 because those are the years for which state data on suicide attempts, plans, and thoughts were available. Data were obtained for both years whenever possible. If not, data for the nearest and most appropriate years were substituted for 2008 and 2009. State personality scores (Rentfrow et al., 2008) were based on data collected between 1999 and 2005, but empirical evidence also pertains effectively to 2008 and 2009 (Elleman et al., 2018). Religiosity data were based on 2008. Depression data were based on 2006 and 2008.

Suicides - The CDC Wonder (2020) interactive source provided population age-adjusted state suicide rates per 100,000 for those 18 years of age and over for the 2008–2009 period. The source also provided age-adjusted suicide rates for males and females and non-age-adjusted suicide rates for younger persons 18–29 years of age and older persons 30 years of age and over. These data were based on the intentional harm (suicide) category of the ICD-10 113 cause list.

Suicide attempts. Percentage estimates of attempted suicides among adults 18 years or over for each state during 2008–2009 were taken from a large-scale survey (Crosby et al., 2011). State sample sizes ranged from 876 to 3,830. Regarding the previous 12 months, respondents answered a question asking whether they had serious thoughts about taking their own lives. Those who answered affirmatively then were asked whether they had any suicide plan and whether they had attempted suicide. The survey also provided suicide attempt rates for four demographic categories: males, females, younger persons, and older persons.

Suicide plans. The present research also utilised state percentage estimates of those with suicide plans among those aged 18 years and over in 2008–2009 (Crosby et al. (2011)). The survey also provided suicide plan rates for the four demographic categories.

Suicide thoughts. State percentage estimates of those with suicide plans among those aged 18 years and over in 2008–2009 also were taken from Crosby et al. (2011). The survey also provided suicide thought rates for the sex and age categories.

Big Five personality variables. Rentfrow et al. (2008) provided Big Five personality z scores for each state and the District of Columbia based on 619,397 respondents to the 44-item Big Five Inventory (John & Srivastava, 1999) in an internet survey conducted from December of 1999 to January of 2005. They reported that the respondents were representative of the American population and drawn from each state proportionately to the 2000 census state populations. The Big Five variables also had high reliabilities with mean individual-level Cronbach alphas of .81 and state-level alphas of .89. Elleman et al. (2018) have demonstrated that such state scores maintained temporal stability and consistent relations to sociodemographic variables from 1999 through 2015.

Socioeconomic status (SES). A composite of two educational and two economic variables gauged SES. For each state in 2008 and 2009, the US Census Bureau (2012) provided the percent of persons 25 years and older who had at least high school graduation and the percent with at least a bachelor's degree. The Bureau of Economic Analysis (2011) provided state per capita personal income for 2008 and 2009. The US Census Bureau (2019) provided the state per cent of persons living below the poverty line in 2008 and 2009. The 2008 and 2009 variables correlated from .89 to 1.00 for each of the four variables. Values were subsequently reversed for the poverty line by multiplying by -1 . The mean score for each state on each of the four resulting variables in 2008 and 2009 was computed and then transformed to a z score. The z values for the four variables then were summed, divided by 4, and subsequently standardised to form a composite SES variable with a Cronbach alpha reliability of .86.

White population per cent. The state per cent of the population self-identified as White in 2008 and 2010 were obtained from the US Census Bureau (2010, 2012). Data for 2009 could not be located. The 2008 and 2010 correlated highly (.94). For each state, the mean of the two years substituted for 2009. They were resulting state 2008 and 2009 values correlated to a high degree (.98). State White population per cent for the present study was the mean of the 2008 and 2009 percentages. Original Hawaii values were beyond -3.00 standard deviations and were reset to that mark to prevent outlier distortions in relevant correlations.

Urban population per cent. State urban population in 2000 and 2010 (Iowa State University, 2019) served as the basis for producing prorated values for 2008 and 2009. Correlations between the 2000 and 2010 values, and between the prorated 2008 and 2009 values, each rounded to 1.00. For each state, the mean of the resulting 2008 and 2009 values served as the urban population percent.

The Bureau of Labor Statistics (2010) furnished annual state unemployment rates for 2008 and 2009. The two rates correlated highly (.93). For each state, the mean for the two years was used here.

Religiosity. State religiosity was assessed through Gallup Poll Daily tracking throughout 2008 (Newport, 2009). Phone interviews with representative state samples of those 18 and over produced a database of 355,334 respondents who were asked, 'Is religion an important part of your daily life?' The state percentage answering affirmatively served as the religiosity variable.

Depression. Reeves et al. (2011) reported state prevalence estimates of depression among those 18 and over in the previous two weeks for 2006 and 2008 using responses to phone interviews conducted by the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) through the Behavioural Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS). The survey included 38 states in 2006, seven remaining states in 2008, and nine states in 2006 and 2008. Kentucky, New Jersey, North Carolina, Pennsylvania, and South Dakota did not provide any data. State depression prevalence rates for 2008–2009 in the present study were based on 2006 if that was the sole assessment year and 2008 if that was the only year assessed. If both 2006 and 2008 were assessed, the mean for the two years served as the 2008–2009 value. For those five states not assessed, the mean of 16.75 for the other states served as a 2008–2009 substitute.

Analytic strategy

After computing descriptive statistics and correlations, sequential multiple regression strategies were planned to determine relations of the Big Five personality variables and the six demographic control variables to state rates of suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts. The six state demographic variables (SES, White population per cent, urban population per cent, unemployment rate, religiosity, and depression) were entered as a block on the first step and consequently controlled for each equation. The Big Five were entered on the second step in stepwise mode.

The study employed two-tailed tests and an alpha of .05. Both population and sample are the same 50 states, thus negating the logic of providing confidence intervals. It could be argued that inferential statistics are neither required nor logical when the population is the sample. However, reported significance tests suggest comparison benchmarks for those in a study in which a sample of this size contains randomly selected cases from a larger population.

Although Bonferroni corrections (e.g., Cabin & Mitchell, 2000; Rice, 1989) remain quite controversial, they are provided for the many correlations and multiple regressions in the present report. Such alpha level adjustments are made by dividing the accepted standard of .05 by the number of correlates or predictors of each variable considered in the correlations or regressions. The result is that an often much lower and conservative probability (*p*) value is necessary for the relation in question to be accepted as statistically significant. The statistical results and their discussion in the present study are predicated on the original alpha levels, but the Bonferroni corrections also are included in the tabled results and briefly discussed for readers who might prefer a much more cautious approach. This was judged to be a wise strategy given the exploratory nature of the research and the reluctance to dismiss potentially important relations simply because they were exposed to the potent power reducing effects of an extraordinarily conservative statistical threshold.

RESULTS

Table 1 displays mean, standard deviations, and Pearson correlations for the 15 variables in the study. Note that all suicide rates are expressed as the number of persons per 100,000 population, while all suicide attempt, plan, and thought rates are expressed as the percent of the respondents in the Crosby et al. (2011) survey. Note that the state Big Five z scores are based on the 50 states and Washington, DC; but the following analyses include only the 50 states. The state SES composite scores are expressed as z scores, and the other five control variables are expressed as estimated state percentages.

Most noteworthy among the Pearson correlations, suicide rates correlated significantly with neuroticism (–.50), agreeableness (–.30), suicide thoughts (.38), depression (.39), and urban population per cent (–.31). Suicide attempts correlated significantly with suicide plans (.66), suicide thoughts (.57), and White population percent (.30), but not with suicide rates or any Big Five personality variables. As well, suicide plans correlated with suicide thoughts (.76), depression (.29), White population per cent (.38), unemployment rate (.30), and religiosity (–.40). Suicide thoughts also correlated with depression (.36), White population per cent (.49), and religiosity (–.34).

The relation of the two Big Five variables (neuroticism and agreeableness) to suicide rates but not to the rates of suicide attempts, plans, or thoughts, and the intercorrelation of suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts, prompted a principal components analysis of these four suicide phenomena. The results are shown in Table 2. Two components were extracted with eigenvalues greater than 1.00, which cumulatively accounted for 87.1% of the variance. Suicide attempts, plans, and thoughts each had heavy positive loadings

on Component 1 (i.e., .78, .92, and .91, respectively), while suicides had a small positive loading of .33, barely above the conventional .30 for consideration. In contrast, suicides had a heavy positive loading, and suicide attempt had a moderate negative loading on Component 2 (i.e., .91 and $-.48$, respectively), while the loadings for suicide plans and suicide thoughts were well below the conventional .30 threshold (i.e., $-.08$ and $.15$, respectively). Component 1 can be referred to most aptly as the suicidal behaviour and ideation (SBI) factor, and Component 2 can be best referred to as a suicide (S) factor.

Table 3 displays the results of sequential multiple regression equations with the SBI factor scores and the S factor scores serving as the criterion variables. In each of the two equations, the six demographic variables were entered as a block on the first step, and the Big Five were selected in stepwise mode on the second. In Equation 1, with SBI factor scores as the criterion, the six controls accounted for a significant 42.9% of the variance, but no Big Five variables were selected. The sole significant β occurred for the White population percent (.43).

In Equation 2, with S factor scores as the criterion, the six controls accounted only for a nonsignificant 21.6% of the variance. However, neuroticism and agreeableness emerged as significant predictors. Neuroticism accounted for another 35.3% of the criterion variance, and agreeableness accounted for a final increment of 10.6%. Significant β s occurred for neuroticism ($-.68$), SES ($-.44$), agreeableness ($-.40$), and urban population percent ($-.27$).

Table 4 presents the sequential multiple regression equation results pertaining to the whole population with suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts analysed separately. In Equation 1, with suicide rates as the criterion, the six demographic variables jointly accounted for a significant 29.8% of the criterion variance. The only predictors to emerge from the stepwise selection were neuroticism and agreeableness. Neuroticism accounted for an additional 32.2% of the criterion variance, and agreeableness accounted for a final increment of 14.4%. For the full equation, the standardized regression coefficients (β s) were significant for neuroticism ($-.66$), SES ($-.53$), agreeableness ($-.47$), and urban population per cent ($-.23$).

In Equation 2, with suicide attempt rates as the criterion, the six demographic variables jointly accounted for only a nonsignificant 21.2% of the variance. No Big Five personality variables were selected in stepwise mode. The β was significant only for the White population percent (.38).

In Equation 3, with suicide plan rates as the criterion, the six demographic variables jointly accounted for a significant 39.6% of the variance. No Big Five personality variables were selected for entry. The β was significant only for the unemployment rate (.37).

In Equation 4, with suicide thought rates as the criterion, the six demographic variables jointly accounted for a significant 46.2% of the variance. No Big Five personality variables were selected. The β s were significant for the White population per cent (.48) and urban population per cent (.41).

Table 5 shows the Pearson correlations between suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide attempts for the whole population, males, females, younger persons, and older persons. Notably, suicides and suicide attempts were not correlated for any of the five demographic groups. Suicides and suicidal plans also were not correlated for any of the five groups, while suicides and suicide thoughts only were correlated for the whole population (.38), females (.39), and older persons (.44). In contrast, suicide attempts correlated highly with suicide plans for the whole population (.66), males (.78), females (.56), younger persons (.55), and older persons (.59). Suicide attempts also correlated with suicide thoughts for the whole population (.57), males (.58), females (.46), and older persons (.41). Suicide plans and thoughts also correlated highly for the whole population (.76), males (.75), females (.77), younger persons (.60), and older persons (.70).

Table 6 displays the Pearson correlations of the suicide, suicide attempt, suicide plan, and suicide thought variables with the Big Five and the six control variables for males, females, younger persons, and older persons. Most notably, in the present context, suicide and neuroticism correlated negatively for males ($-.47$), females ($-.51$), younger persons ($-.48$), and older persons ($-.46$). Correlations between suicide and agreeableness were negative for all four groups but only significant for females ($-.34$) and younger persons ($-.37$). On the other hand, suicide attempts did not correlate significantly with neuroticism for any four groups except older persons (.29). Agreeableness also did not correlate with suicide attempts for any of the groups. Neither neuroticism nor agreeableness correlated with suicide plans or suicide thoughts for any of the four demographic groups.

Table 7 shows the details of the sequential multiple regression equation results pertaining to males, females, younger persons, and older persons with suicide rates, suicide attempt rates, suicide plan rates, and suicide thought rates serving as the criterion variables. With suicide rates as the criterion (Equation 1 through Equation 4), neuroticism and agreeableness emerged as significant predictors for males, females, younger persons, and older persons.

Together, these two Big Five personality variables accounted for between 38.8% and 48.8% of the suicide rate variance, and the significant β coefficients ranged from $-.61$ to $-.68$ for neuroticism and from $-.28$ to $-.59$ for agreeableness across the four groups. Extraversion also surfaced as a minor Big Five predictor for females and older persons. It accounted for a final 3.3% of the criterion variance for females and a final 4.4% of the variance for older persons. The significant β s were $-.25$ and $-.28$, respectively. In stark contrast, with one exception, no Big Five personally dimensions emerged as predictors of suicide attempts, suicide plans, or suicide thoughts (Equation 5 through Equation 16). The lone exception occurred for older persons with suicide attempts as the criterion in Equation 8, wherein neuroticism accounted for a final increment of 7.4%, and the significant β was $.29$.

Regarding the independent predictive capacities of the six sociodemographic control variables in Table 7, with suicide rates as the criterion (Equation 1 through Equation 4), SES had significant

β s for males, females, and older persons ranging from $-.49$ to $-.68$. Urban population percent had significant β s of $-.27$ for males and $-.34$ for younger persons. Also, the unemployment rate had a significant β of $-.23$ for younger persons, and the White population percent had a significant β of $.25$ for older persons.

With suicide attempt rates as the criterion (Equation 5 through Equation 8), none of the six control variables was a predictor for males, females, or younger persons. For older persons, the unemployment rate had a significant β of $.38$, and the White population percent had one of $.35$.

With suicide plan rates as the criterion (Equation 9 through Equation 12), the unemployment rate had a significant β of $.41$ for males and one of $.43$ for older persons. Religiosity had a significant β of $-.45$ for females and one of $-.47$ for younger persons.

Finally, with suicide thought rates as the criterion (Equation 13 through Equation 16), the White population percent had a significant β s of $.41$ for males, $.40$ for females, and $.52$ for older persons. Urban population percent had a significant β of $.54$ for females and one of $.45$ for older persons. SES had a significant β of $-.54$ for females.

Table 1
Means, Standard Deviations, and Pearson Correlations for Suicides, Attempts, Plans, Thoughts, Big Five, and Control Variables

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.
1. Suicides	13.28	3.54														
2. Suicide attempts	.48	.25	-.09													
3. Suicide plans	1.11	.46	.21	.66***												
4. Suicide thoughts	3.94	1.04	.38**	.57***	.76***											
5. Openness to experience	-.07	.89	-.21	.17	.14	.16										
6. Conscientiousness	.01	1.01	.06	-.10	-.27	-.07	.05									
7. Extraversion	-.03	.98	-.19	.04	-.14	-.10	-.51***	.43**								
8. Agreeableness	.04	.96	-.30*	-.04	-.16	-.16	-.12	.67***	.55***							
9. Neuroticism	.01	1.01	-.50***	.21	-.06	-.23	.13	-.27	-.15	-.09						
10. SES	.00	1.00	-.23	-.01	.09	.03	.14	-.45***	-.17	-.23	-.22					
11. White population %	81.14	10.33	.26	.30*	.38**	.49***	-.04	.01	.14	.09	-.10	.20				
12. Urban population %	73.31	14.61	-.31*	.09	.01	.12	.39**	.06	-.07	-.09	-.20	.31*	-.33*			
13. Unemployment rate	6.86	1.59	-.15	.21	.30*	.13	.31*	.04	-.15	-.04	.23	-.34*	-.26	.26		
14. Religiosity	64.06	9.97	-.04	-.17	-.40**	-.34*	-.32*	.54***	.38**	.45***	.12	-.70***	-.37**	-.21	.06	
15. Depression	16.75	2.41	.39**	.21	.29*	.36**	.10	-.02	-.17	-.07	.06	-.19	.51***	-.46***	-.01	-.07

Note: The correlations in italics are those that did not reach the Bonferroni corrected significance level of .0035714 (i.e., .05/14).

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Table 2
Total Variance Explained in the Principal Component Analysis of Suicides, Suicide Attempts, Suicide Plans, and Suicide Thoughts, and Their Loadings

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loading			Loadings			
	Total	% of variance	Cumulative % of variance	Total	% of variance	Cumulative % of variance	Suicides	Attempts	Plans	Thoughts
1	2.39	59.74	59.74	2.39	59.74	59.74	.33	.78	.92	.91
2	1.10	27.36	87.11	1.10	27.36	87.11	.91	-.48	-.08	.15
3	.29	7.35	94.46							
4	.22	5.55	100.00							

Table 3
 Sequential Multiple Regression Equations Demonstrating the Relations of the Big Five Personality Variables to Factor 1 and Factor 2 Scores When Controlling for the Six Demographic Variables

Equation	Criterion ^a	Step	Entry method	Predictor pool	Stepwise predictors	df	R ² change	F	Significant independent predictors	β	t			
1	Component 1	1	forced block	Six demographic controls Big Five	(none entered)	6, 43	.429	5.38***	<i>White population %</i>	.43	2.77**			
		2	stepwise											
2	Component 2	1	forced block	Six demographic controls Big Five	Neuroticism	6, 43	.216	1.98	Neuroticism	-.68	-7.07***			
		2	stepwise									SES	-.44	-2.90**
												Agreeableness	-.40	-3.65***
				<i>Urban population %</i>	-.27	-2.25*								

Note: The variables and values in italics are those that did not reach the Bonferroni corrected significance level of .0045454 (i.e., .05/11).

^aComponent 1 is the suicidal behavior and ideation (SBI) factor and Component 2 is the suicide (S) factor.

p* < .05. *p* < .01. ****p* < .001.

Table 4
 Sequential Multiple Regression Equations Demonstrating the Relations of the Big Five Personality Variables to Suicides, Suicide Attempts, Suicide Plans, and Suicide Thoughts When Controlling for the Six Demographic Variables

Equation	Criterion	Step	Entry method	Predictor pool	Stepwise predictors	df	R ² change	F	Significant independent predictors	β	t			
1	Suicides	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i> Big Five	Neuroticism	6, 43	.298	3.05*	Neuroticism	-.66	-8.04***			
		2	stepwise									SES	-.53	-4.07***
												Agreeableness	-.47	-5.02***
				<i>Urban population %</i>	-.23	-2.22*								
2	Suicide attempts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls Big Five	(none entered)	6, 43	.212	1.92	<i>White population %</i>	.38	2.09*			
		2	stepwise											
3	Suicide plans	1	forced block	Six demographic controls Big Five	(none entered)	6, 43	.396	4.71***	<i>Unemployment rate</i>	.37	2.55*			
		2	stepwise											
4	Suicide thoughts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls Big Five	(none entered)	6, 43	.462	6.15***	<i>White population %</i>	.48	3.17**			
		2	stepwise									<i>Urban population %</i>	.41	2.83**

Note: The variables and values in italics are those that did not reach the Bonferroni corrected significance level of .0045454 (i.e., .05/11).

p* < .05. *p* < .01. ****p* < .001.

Table 5
 Pearson Correlations Among Suicides, Attempts, Plans, and Thoughts for the Whole Population, Males, Females, Younger Persons, and Older Persons

Suicide variable	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.	15.	16.	17.	18.	19.
1. Suicides																			
2. Attempts	-.09																		
3. Plans	.21	.66***																	
4. Thoughts	.38**	.57***	.76***																
5. Male suicides	.99***	-.12	.19	.34*															
6. Male attempts	-.06	.76***	.63***	.41**	-.07														
7. Male plans	.09	.55***	.79***	.46***	.07	.78***													
8. Male thoughts	.28*	.54***	.73***	.77***	.25	.58***	.75***												
9. Female suicides	.95***	-.03	.26	.46***	.91***	-.01	.12	.37**											
10. Female attempts	-.12	.75***	.39**	.43**	-.15	.18	.05	.22	-.05										
11. Female plans	.22	.47***	.74***	.70***	.19	.19	.19	.34*	.26	.56***									
12. Female thoughts	.33*	.42**	.56***	.89***	.30*	.18	.12	.40**	.39**	.46***	.77***								
13. Younger suicides	.87***	-.15	.01	.15	.86***	-.15	-.05	.10	.76***	-.14	.05	.13							
14. Younger attempts	.04	.65***	.53***	.44***	.04	.46***	.37**	.34*	.06	.57***	.48***	.37**	-.04						
15. Younger plans	.21	.33*	.62***	.53***	.19	.23	.36**	.37**	.23	.28	.60***	.48***	.15	.55***					
16. Younger thoughts	.23	.26	.40**	.57***	.21	.12	.13	.33*	.27	.25	.50***	.58***	.21	.25	.60***				
17. Older suicides	.96***	-.07	.29*	.45***	.95***	-.02	.13	.33*	.95***	-.10	.30*	.40**	.70***	.06	.21	.23			
18. Older attempts	-.28*	.81***	.53***	.38**	-.30*	.68***	.44***	.41**	-.19	.58***	.36*	.26	-.36*	.29*	.17	.11	-.21		
19. Older plans	.14	.63***	.91***	.66***	.12	.64***	.77***	.72***	.21	.32*	.63***	.44***	-.08	.40**	.32*	.21	.24	.59***	
20. Older thoughts	.35*	.56***	.75***	.97***	.31*	.43**	.49***	.79***	.43**	.41**	.66***	.83***	.09	.41**	.42**	.34*	.44**	.41**	.70***

Note: The correlations in italics are those that did not reach the Bonferroni corrected significance level of .0026315 (i.e., .05/19).

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Table 6
 Pearson Correlations of the Male, Female, Younger Person, and Older Person Suicide Variables with Big Five and Control Variables

Suicide variable	Openness	Conscientiousness	Extraversion	Agreeableness	Neuroticism	SES	White population %	Urban population %	Unemployment rate	Religiosity	Depression
1. Male suicides	-.24	.08	-.16	-.27	-.47***	-.27	.27	-.37**	-.16	.02	.40**
2. Male attempts	.13	-.10	-.00	-.01	.23	-.08	.29*	-.04	.25	-.14	.18
3. Male plans	.09	-.24	-.15	-.13	.06	.06	.21	-.04	.29*	-.23	.21
4. Male thoughts	.08	-.17	-.10	-.11	-.18	.11	.47***	-.05	.11	-.29*	.37**
5. Female suicides	-.04	.03	-.29*	-.34*	-.51***	-.22	.19	-.15	-.03	-.15	.35*
6. Female attempts	.15	-.09	.02	-.04	.11	.05	.17	.20	.11	-.16	.17
7. Female plans	.14	-.17	-.05	-.11	-.12	.07	.35*	.05	.15	-.38**	.23
8. Female thoughts	.19	.03	-.07	-.15	-.20	-.03	.36**	.23	.12	-.27	.24
9. Young suicides	-.38**	-.04	-.07	-.37**	-.48***	-.09	.16	-.35*	-.36**	.01	.24
10. Younger attempts	.11	.05	.01	.03	.21	-.20	.18	-.04	.07	-.03	.33*
11. Younger plans	.02	-.27	-.16	-.16	.03	-.04	.13	-.11	.11	-.22	.14
12. Younger thoughts	.13	-.18	-.07	-.11	-.18	.13	.26	-.03	-.07	-.31*	.18
13. Older suicides	-.07	.10	-.25	-.25	-.46***	-.28*	.26	-.24	-.01	-.06	.41**
14. Older attempts	.19	-.19	.01	-.08	.29*	.02	.19	.15	.39**	-.20	.11
15. Older plans	.18	-.20	-.06	-.11	-.07	.10	.34*	.04	.34*	-.37**	.26
16. Older thoughts	.16	-.03	-.10	-.15	-.19	.01	.49***	.15	.17	-.31*	.35*

Note: The correlations in italics are those that did not reach the Bonferroni corrected significance level of .0031250 (i.e., .05/16).

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Table 7
 Sequential Multiple Regression Equations Demonstrating the Relations of the Big Five Personality Variables to Suicides, Suicide Attempts, Suicide Plans, and Suicide Thoughts for Males, Females, Younger Persons, and Older Persons When Controlling for the Six Demographic Variables

Equation	Category	Criterion	Step	Entry method	Predictor pool	Stepwise predictors	df	R ² change	F	Significant independent predictors	β	t
1	Male	Suicides	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>		6, 43	.313	3.26*	Neuroticism	-.64	-7.61***
						2	stepwise	<i>Big Five</i>	Neuroticism	1, 42	.300	32.55***
								Agreeableness	1, 41	.142	23.68***	Agreeableness
									<i>Urban population %</i>	-.27	-2.61*	
2	Female	Suicides	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>		6, 43	.313	3.27**	Neuroticism	-.68	-8.45***
						2	stepwise	<i>Big Five</i>	Neuroticism	1, 42	.327	38.19***
								Agreeableness	1, 41	.108	17.69***	Agreeableness
									<i>Extraversion</i>	-.25	-2.47*	
3	Younger	Suicides	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>		6, 43	.260	2.52*	Neuroticism	-.61	-7.21***
						2	stepwise	<i>Big Five</i>	Neuroticism	1, 42	.261	22.92***
								Agreeableness	1, 41	.227	37.10***	Urban population %
									<i>Unemployment rate</i>	-.23	-2.28*	
4	Older	Suicides	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>		6, 43	.316	3.31**	Neuroticism	-.65	-7.54***
						2	stepwise	<i>Big Five</i>	Neuroticism	1, 42	.299	32.56***
								Agreeableness	1, 41	.089	12.35***	<i>Extraversion</i>
									<i>Agreeableness</i>	-.28	-2.71**	
									<i>White population %</i>	.25	2.02*	
5	Male	Suicide attempts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls		6, 43	.206	1.86			

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			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
6	Female	Suicide attempts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.151	1.27				
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
7	Younger	Suicide attempts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.192	1.70				
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
8	Older	Suicide attempts	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>	<i>Neuroticism</i>	<i>6, 43</i>	<i>.268</i>	<i>2.62*</i>	<i>Unemployment rate</i>	<i>.38</i>	<i>2.38*</i>	
			2	stepwise	<i>Big Five</i>		<i>1, 42</i>	<i>.074</i>	<i>4.72*</i>	<i>White population %</i>	<i>.35</i>	<i>2.08*</i>	
										<i>Neuroticism</i>	<i>.29</i>	<i>2.17*</i>	
9	Male	Suicide plans	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.210	1.91	<i>Unemployment rate</i>	<i>.41</i>	<i>2.46*</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
10	Female	Suicide plans	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>	(none entered)	<i>6, 43</i>	<i>.292</i>	<i>2.95*</i>	<i>Religiosity</i>	<i>-.45</i>	<i>-2.19*</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
11	Younger	Suicide plans	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.138	1.15	<i>Religiosity</i>	<i>-.47</i>	<i>-2.07*</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
12	Older	Suicide plans	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.379	4.37**	<i>Unemployment rate</i>	<i>.43</i>	<i>2.89**</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
13	Male	Suicide thoughts	1	forced block	<i>Six demographic controls</i>	(none entered)	<i>6, 43</i>	<i>.323</i>	<i>3.41**</i>	<i>White population %</i>	<i>.41</i>	<i>2.44*</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
14	Female	Suicide thoughts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.417	5.13***	<i>Urban population %</i>	<i>.54</i>	<i>3.57***</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)				<i>SES</i>	<i>-.53</i>	<i>-2.65*</i>	
										<i>White population %</i>	<i>.40</i>	<i>2.57*</i>	
15	Younger	Suicide thoughts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.144	1.20				
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)							
16	Older	Suicide thoughts	1	forced block	Six demographic controls	(none entered)	6, 43	.484	6.73***	<i>White population %</i>	<i>.52</i>	<i>3.52***</i>	
			2	stepwise	Big Five	(none entered)				<i>Urban population %</i>	<i>.45</i>	<i>3.14**</i>	

Note: The variables and values in italics are those that did not reach the Bonferroni corrected significance level of .0045454 (i.e., .05/11).

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

DISCUSSION

What stands out most in the present research results is that the multiple regression results consistently demonstrated that neuroticism and agreeableness were predictors of state suicide rates but not of suicide attempts, plans, or thoughts. This pattern occurred when the SBI and S factor scores or the four individual suicidal phenomena variables served as the criteria. Higher suicide rates were associated with *lower* neuroticism for the whole population, males, females, younger persons, and older persons. Higher suicide rates also were associated with *lower* agreeableness for each of these five categories. The only exception to this pattern among the 22 regression equations occurred for the older person category in which neuroticism was a modest predictor of suicide attempts, wherein higher suicide attempt rates were associated with *higher* neuroticism. Extraversion also emerged as a minor predictor of suicide in the female and older person categories, with a small association between higher suicide rates and lower extraversion.

The magnitude of the variance accounted for in suicide rates by personality was not trivial. Neuroticism and agreeableness together accounted for considerably more variance than the six-state control variables (SES, unemployment rate, religiosity, depression, White population percent, and urban population per cent) after the variance in suicide rates that could be accounted for by these six variables already was removed. Based on the six relevant multiple regression equations (i.e., Equation 2 in Table 3, Equation 1 in Table 4, and Equation 1, 2, 3, and 4 in Table 7), the variance in suicide rates accounted for by neuroticism and agreeableness together was 22.8% to 112.5% greater than the variance accounted for by the six control variables combined. The mean additional contribution to the variance accounted for in the suicide rate criteria was 59.9%. Most striking was the finding that the additional suicide rate variance accounted for in the S factor score criterion by neuroticism and agreeableness together was 112.5% greater than the total increment attributable to the six control variables and that the additional variance accounted for by neuroticism alone was 63.4% greater.

It should be noted that two main outcome variables—suicide rates and suicide attempt rates—were not correlated with each other in the present state-level study. The independence of these two criteria of suicidal phenomena is evident from the nonsignificant negative Pearson correlations of $-.09$ for the whole population, $-.07$ for males, $-.05$ for females, $-.04$ for younger $-.21$ for older persons. Furthermore, the principal components analysis revealed that the suicide rate loads heavily on the S factor, and the suicide attempt rate loads heavily on the SBI factor. Therefore, it is not surprising that the multiple regression predictor patterns for suicide rates are quite different from the predictor pattern for suicide attempt rates. From the present results, it is evident that personality dimensions – particularly neuroticism and agreeableness – predict suicide rates but not suicide attempt rates, except for the older person category. Neuroticism predicts positively rather than the negative direction found in it the relations between neuroticism and suicide rates. The relatively high level of intercorrelation between suicide attempt, plan, and thought rates across the whole population, males, females, three younger persons, and older persons, as well as the high loadings of these three suicidal phenomena on the SBI factor in the principal components analysis, also suggest why personality also is not related to suicide plans and thoughts.

The relation of neuroticism to suicide at the state level was expected and is consistent with the corresponding results of earlier state-level research (i.e., Lester & Voracek, 2013; McCann, 2010; Voracek, 2009). The pattern of results for agreeableness also was generally expected, but somewhat less confidently so than was the pattern for neuroticism. It bolsters the similar results found by McCann (2010) and Voracek (2009) but runs counter to the lack of relationship found by Lester and Voracek (2013). However, the present work is the first to find these relations with such a large set of statistical controls and the whole population, males, females, younger persons, and older persons.

Although not the central focus of the present research, it is appropriate and beneficial to briefly summarize the contributions of each of the six control variables as predictors of suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts. Across the 20 multiple regression equations excluding the two using SBI and S factor scores, based on both significant and nonsignificant contributions, the six demographic controls accounted for a mean of 28.9% of the criterion variance, with values ranging from a nonsignificant 13.8% to a significant 48.6%. According to the independent contributions indicated by the significant β coefficients for the full equations excluding the two based on factor scores, higher suicide rates were associated with lower SES for the whole population, males, females, and older persons, with lower urban population percent for the whole population, males, and younger persons, with the *lower* unemployment rate for younger persons, and with higher White population percent for older persons. Higher suicide attempt rates were associated with higher White population percent for the whole population and older persons and a higher unemployment rate for older persons. Higher suicide plan rates were associated with higher White population percent for the whole

population, with the higher unemployment rate for males and older persons and lower religiosity for females and younger persons. Finally, higher suicide thought rates were associated with higher White population percent for the whole population, males, females, and older persons, with higher urban population percent for the whole population, females, and older persons, and with lower SES for females.

The research of McCann (2010) supported the present relation between suicide and SES and between urban population percent, but not the relation between suicide and White population per cent. Vorcek (2009) or Lester and Voracek (2013) tested None of these relations involving these demographic control variables. In individual-level research, the present finding of a negative relation between SES and suicides is well supported (e.g., Agerbo et al., 2006; Page et al., 2014), but the general lack of relation between SES and suicide attempts, plans, and thoughts is contrary to what has been found (e.g., Kim et al., 2016; Taylor et al., 2004). Other research with individuals as the analytical units has found that suicide is associated with higher unemployment (e.g., Milner et al., 2013), greater urbanisation (e.g., Goldman-Mellor et al., 2018), and being White (e.g., Garlow et al., 2005). Individual-level relations also have been reported between suicide attempts and being White (e.g., Stoliker & Galli, 2020), suicide plans and thoughts and being White (e.g., Ammerman et al., 2020), and suicide plans and lower religiosity (e.g., Toussaint et al., 2015). However, non-supportive results also have been reported. For example, the relation between suicide thoughts and urbanisation was not supported by Goldman-Mellor et al. (2018). Therefore, existing individual-level research at least partially supports the present state-level results.

A foundational assumption of geographical psychology (e.g., Rentfrow, 2014; Rentfrow et al., 2008) is that the aggregate position on a dispositional dimension in a geographic area reflects the central tendency of the area's residents on that dimension and is associated with the prevalence in that area of the psychological and behavioural proclivities related to that dispositional dimension. The perspective also recognizes that aggregate-level and individual-level relations are logically independent. It cannot simply be *assumed* that aggregate-level results generalize to the individual level (Robinson 1950), nor can it simply be *assumed* that individual-level results generalize to the aggregate level (Pettigrew 1997). This does not mean that state-level results cannot stem from and be consistent with individual-level relations, but it does mean that cautious interpretation of cross-level extrapolations is necessary. The degree of confidence in interpretations should be dependent upon empirical verification.

So, with ample caution, it is plausible to speculate that relations found in the present research between state-level variables exist because of corresponding relations at the individual level. The best current interpretation is that the state-level relations mirror and result from the aggregation of individual-level relations. It should be noted that other state-level variables that might have explained the present results and which also have at least similar counterparts at the individual level do not do so. This includes state differences in SES, White population percent, urban population percent, unemployment rate, religiosity, and mental depression.

Compared to individual-level research results, the present state-level multiple regression findings involving the relation of neuroticism to suicides are largely but not wholly incompatible (e.g., Batty et al., 2018; Draper et al., 2014; Tsoh et al., 2005; Useda et al., 2007), while those involving the relation of agreeableness to suicides roughly correspond (e.g., Batty et al., 2018; Draper et al., 2014; Mousavi et al., 2015). Those involving the lack of relation of neuroticism to suicide attempts tend to be discordant (e.g., Rappaport et al., 2017; Su et al., 2018; Useda et al., 2007; Wasserman, 2016), while those pertaining to the lack of relation between agreeableness and suicide attempts correspond to at least one individual-level study (Stankovic et al., 2006).

However, none of the preceding individual-level studies used the same sequential multiple regression analytic strategy as the present state-level research. Nor did any of those studies use appropriately comparable control variables. Until research with individuals as the analytic units is conducted using comparable variables and a similar analytic approach, it is premature to firmly conclude that any of the state-level relations found in the present study do not mirror individual-level results. Although the present findings are rather convincing, further empirical inquiry is needed to bolster or refute the tentative conclusion that the present state-level results stem from individual-level dynamics. More research is warranted at both the aggregate and the individual level regarding relations between the Big Five personality factors, the six demographic variables, and suicides, suicide attempts, suicide plans, and suicide thoughts to reconcile discrepancies, not only at the individual or the state level but also aimed at relations between the two levels of analysis.

With Bonferroni adjustments, regarding the correlates of suicidal phenomena in Table 1, only the following correlations were significant: suicide rates and neuroticism (-.50), suicide attempts and suicide plans (.66), suicide attempts and suicidal thoughts (.57), suicide plans, and suicide thoughts (.76), and suicide thoughts and White population percent (.49). In Table 3, regarding the regression coefficients for independent predictors of suicidal phenomena, only the following were significant: Component 2, on which suicide rates

loaded heavily, was predicted by neuroticism ($\beta = -.68$) and agreeableness ($\beta = -.40$). In Table 4, with suicide rates as the criterion, only the following were independent predictors: neuroticism ($\beta = -.66$), agreeableness ($\beta = -.47$), and SES ($\beta = -.53$). With the other three suicidal phenomena as criteria, the only remaining significant predictor was the White population per cent ($\beta = .48$) with suicidal thoughts as the criterion. Regarding the male, female, younger, and older subcategories and the prediction of the four suicidal phenomena in Table 7, only the following were significant independent predictors: neuroticism was a negatively signed predictor of male, female, older, and younger suicide rates; agreeableness was a negative predictor of male, female, and older suicide rates; SES was a negative predictor of male, female, and older suicide rates; urban population percent was a negative predictor of younger suicide rates; urban population percent was a positively signed predictor of suicide thoughts for females and older persons, and White population per cent was a positive predictor of suicide thoughts for older persons.

Overall, with Bonferroni adjustments to the results of the multiple regression equations in Table 3, 4, and 7, White population per cent ceased to predict Component 1, suicide attempts, older suicides and attempts, and male and female suicide thoughts. Urban population percent ceased to predict Component 2, suicides, suicide thoughts, and male suicides. The unemployment rate ceased to predict suicide plans, younger suicides, older suicide attempts, and male and older suicide plans. Extraversion ceased to predict female and older suicides. Agreeableness ceased to predict older suicides. Neuroticism ceased to predict older suicide attempts. Religiosity ceased to predict female and younger suicide plans. Finally, SES ceased to predict female suicide thoughts.

The need for the application of the Bonferroni procedure in this exploratory research is questionable and perhaps imprudent. Critics of the Bonferroni approach (e.g., Armstrong, 2014; Nakagawa, 2004) point out that such statistical correction decreases the chances of making a Type 1 inferential error but can greatly increase the chances of making Type 2 errors, and that its routine use should not be encouraged. Instead, for example, Nakagawa (2004) suggests that attention should be placed on observed effect sizes such as r and R^2 , using Cohen's (1988) correlation benchmarks of .10, .30, and .50, respectively, for small, medium, and large effect sizes. Given the relatively low N of 50 in the present analyses, Pearson correlations and standardized regression coefficients up to the low .40s were deemed nonsignificant with the Bonferroni correction. However, as mentioned earlier in the discussion of analytic strategy, because the sample and the populations are the same in the present study, there is much room for less emphasis on statistical significance and inference matters. Nevertheless, even with Bonferroni corrections, the most important findings of the present research remained intact: Higher suicide rates still were associated with lower neuroticism and lower agreeableness, while rates of suicide attempts, plans, and thoughts related to neither neuroticism nor agreeableness.

Limitations and issues

The usual cautions regarding the interpretation of correlational evidence of a link between personality and suicidal phenomena apply to the present study: Causal relations cannot be inferred from correlations. However, it is implausible that state levels of suicidal phenomena cause differences in state personality or state demographic variables. The converse is more likely. An unknown 'third variable' explanation remains possible. However, six of the more likely candidate sociodemographic variables (SES, White population per cent, urban population per cent, unemployment rate, religiosity, and depression) have been considered, and they do not explain. Therefore, even though the evidence is based on the correlations inherent in multiple regression equations, the speculation remains that the causal direction is from personality to suicidal phenomena. Similar directional speculation can be applied to the correlational evidence linking the sociodemographic variables to suicidal phenomena.

The multiple regression analysis of small samples may raise concerns for some readers. A degree of instability in predictors and regression coefficients can occur when the case-to-predictor ratio is far from optimal. However, such potential inferential drawbacks are minimised in the present research. Inferential statistics estimate the confidence that can be placed in generalizing to a population from a representative sample, but the present study has the unusual circumstance that the population and sample are the same—the 50 states. Therefore, the 'population' parameters do not have to be estimated through inferential statistics because they are already known from the 'sample' characteristics. Furthermore, regression strategies with small samples often have been used successfully (e.g., Barber, 2015; McCann, 2008, 2018; Pesta et al., 2012; Simonton, 1986).

Some of the effect sizes based on correlations, regression coefficients, and variance in the dependent variables may be larger than those produced in research with individuals as the analytical units. This is expected (e.g., Erikson et al., 1993; Ostroff, 1993). Measurement errors largely cancel each other in the aggregation process.

This results in elevated effect sizes, but they are also more stable than those computed with individuals rather than aggregates as the units of analysis. Aggregation also enhances the likelihood of statistically significant findings.

Because of the capacity of the geographical psychology approach (e.g., Rentfrow & Jokela, 2016) to produce results based on aggregates that possess less error variance, the present results provide signals for further nomothetic empirical inquiry at the more conventional individual level of analysis to search deeper for results that might not as readily emerge from the individual-level research paradigm (e.g., Ostroff, 1993). The signals emanating from the present results strongly suggest that parallel relations may exist between the corresponding variables at the individual level, giving rise to the relations between personality and suicidal phenomena found here. Nomothetic cross-validation research using similar variables and analytic strategies with individuals as the units of analysis would greatly bolster the conclusions reached here and more adequately alleviate concerns regarding cross-level generalisations (e.g., Robinson, 1950; Pettigrew, 1997).

Perhaps some concern is that the same sample provided state scores for suicide attempts, plans, and thoughts, while scores for suicide were based on official state data for the whole state population. Regarding personality, the results were markedly different for suicide compared to the other three suicidal phenomena. However, suppose it is assumed that the sample of Crosby et al. (2011) was representative of the state population. In that case, the correlation between personality and suicide and the lack of correlation between personality and the other suicide-related variables should be accepted as a genuine difference in the present pattern of findings. Ultimately, the differences between the two sources of data on the results pattern cannot be discerned from the available information.

Of course, with state-level data, the possibility can always be entertained that, for example, those in a state who end their own lives might not be low on neuroticism even though the average state resident is low on that personality dimension. A central assumption of the geographical psychology approach (e.g., Rentfrow et al., 2008) effectively maintains that the state position on a dispositional dimension is related to other state-level indicators according to the tendencies associated with that dimension at the individual level. Nevertheless, in rare circumstances, this assumption could prove untenable. However, it does not seem reasonable to expect such exceptions for so many states that these exceptions drive the state-level relations found in the present study.

Potential applied implications

Such research eventually could lead to a change of focus, or at least a greater depth of field, regarding suicide reduction campaigns and clinical approaches. For example, support indicating that state resident differences in neuroticism predict whether state suicide rates are higher would suggest that state suicide reduction efforts optimally should be adapted to state resident personality profiles. Pervasive preoccupation with suicide attempts may not be the most effective strategy for informational campaigns in states where neuroticism is characteristically lower.

As well, at the clinical level, healthcare professionals may be in danger of missing the mark if they are not particularly vigilant for suicide risk signs in clients from states with characteristically lower resident neuroticism or lower agreeableness, in those who are less neurotic or more disagreeable, or those who do not outwardly display evidence of attempted suicide or suicidal ideation. It also appears that state policymakers and clinicians should be cognizant that lower state SES usually is associated with higher state suicide rates but not with state suicide attempt rates, plan rates, or thought rates. For some of the five demographic groups, state urban population percent, White population percent, unemployment rate, and religiosity also show relations to at least some of the suicide, suicide attempt, suicide plan, and suicide thought variables. Ideally, all these relations should be considered in the context of suicide reduction campaigns and clinical practice.

CONCLUSION

The salient theme in the present research is the view that state residents' Big Five personality within the nonpathological spectrum is important in determining which states have residents more likely to intentionally end their own lives but not which states have residents more likely to attempt suicide or have suicidal ideations. Foremost, the Big Five dimensions of neuroticism and agreeableness have pivotal roles. It also is speculated that these state-level relations stem from parallel individual relations, although the extant research evidence garnered at the individual level is not generally harmonious with such speculation. Nevertheless, this

study has produced novel state-level results with adequate statistical controls that add substantially to the knowledge base on suicidal phenomena. The findings also may eventually contribute to further refinements concerning both suicide reduction campaigns and clinical practices.

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